

AMALIY MASALALARNING KASR TARTIBLI HOSILALI FUNKSIONALLARI

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada xotira va irsiy xossalarga ega bo`lgan qovushqoq elastikning amaliy masalalarini funksiyalarning kasr tartibli hosilasi qatnashgan funkcionallar va kasr tartibli differensial tenglamalar bilan modellashtirilishi ko`rsatib o`tilgan. Funksiyalarning kasr tartibli hosilasi qatnashgan ayrim funkcionallarning ekstremumga ega bo`lishining zaruriy shartlarini keltirib chiqarilgan va mos Eyler–Lagranj tenglamalari hosil qilingan hamda amaliy ahamiyatga ega bo`lgan ayrim masalalar ko`rib chiqilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: funktsional, kasr tartibli variatsion hisob, kasr tartibli hosila, kasr tartibli **integral**, kasr tartibli differensial tenglama, funktsional ekstremumi, Eyler–Lagranj tenglamasi, qovushqoq elastiklik nazariyasi.

Аннотация. В статье рассмотрены функционалы, содержащие дробные производные функций, выведены необходимые условия существования экстремума, получены соответствующие уравнения Эйлера–Лагранжа, а также рассмотрены некоторые задачи, имеющие практическое значение.

Ключевые слова: функционал, дробный вариационный исчисление, дробная производная, дробный интеграл, дробное дифференциальное уравнение, экстремум функционала, уравнение Эйлера–Лагранжа, теория вязкоупругости.

Abstract. The article considers functionals involving fractional derivatives of functions, derives the necessary conditions for the existence of extrema, obtains the corresponding Euler–Lagrange equations, and examines several problems of practical significance.

Keywords: functional, fractional calculus of variations, fractional derivative, fractional integral, fractional differential equation, extremum of a functional, Euler–Lagrange equation, viscoelasticity theory.

Ma'lumki, differensial tenglamalar fan va texnikaning ko`plab amaliy masalalarini matematik ifodalashda foydalaniladi va ularni keltirib chiqarishning juda ko`p matematik vositalari mavjud. Shunday vositalardan biri variatsion hisobdir. So`ngi yillarda kasr tartibli differensial tenglamalar nazariyasi jadal rivojlanmoqda va ular ham ko`plab amaliy masalalarning matematik modeli hisoblanadi. Bunday differensial tenglamalarga mos funkcionallarni umumiy ko`rinishi, ular qanday ko`rinishdagi Eyler–Lagranj tenglamalaridan kelib chiqadi degan savollarga javob berish ham muhimdir. Shuning uchun ushbu ishda kasr tartibli variatsion hisob ya'ni funksiyalarning kasr tartibli hosilasi qatnashgan funkcionallar, ularning ekstremumga ega bo`lishining zaruriy shartlarini keltirib chiqarish va mos Eyler–Lagranj tenglamalarini hosil qilish masalalar bilan shug`ullanamiz.

Mavzuga tegishli asosiy tushunchalarni [1-4] adabiyotlardan topish mumkin. Mavzuga yaqin bo`lgan eng yangi ishlar sifatida [5-9] adabiyotlarni ko`rsatish mumkin.

Ko'plab adabiyotlarda kasr tartibli hosila tushunchasi kasr tartibli integral tushunchasiga teskari amal sifatida kiritiladi. Biz ham avval kasr tartibli integral tushunchasini kiritib, so'ngra kasr tartibli hosila tushunchasini ko'ramiz[1,3,8,9].

Ta'rif. Agar $\varphi(x) \in L_1(a, b)$ bo'lsa, u holda quyidagi ko'rinishdagi integrallar

$$(I_{a+}^{\alpha}\varphi)(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x \frac{\varphi(t)}{(x-t)^{1-\alpha}} dt, \quad x > a, \quad (1)$$

va

$$(I_{b-}^{\alpha}\varphi)(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^b \frac{\varphi(t)}{(t-x)^{1-\alpha}} dt, \quad x < b, \quad (2)$$

mos ravishda Riman-Liuvillnig o'ng tomonlama va chap tomonlama α kasr tartibli integrali deyiladi, bu yerda $\alpha > 0$, $\Gamma(\alpha) = \int_0^{\infty} x^{\alpha-1} e^{-x} dx$ - gamma funksiya. Bu funksiyaning

qiymatlar jadvali mavjud. Ushbu funksiyaning xossalari, qiymatlar jadvali haqidagi ma'lumotlarni Internet saytlari va maxsus funksiyalar yoritilgan adabiyotlardan topish mumkin. Bundan tashqari bu funksiya qiymatlarini Maple va boshqa matematik sistemalar yordamida ham hisoblash mumkin.

Agar $a = 0$ desak, o'ng tomonlama α kasr tartibli integral quyidagi ko'rinishda yoziladi

$$(I_{0+}^{\alpha}\varphi)(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^x \frac{\varphi(t)}{(x-t)^{1-\alpha}} dt.$$

Kasr tartibli hosila kasr tartibli integralga teskari amal sifatida aniqlanadi. Buning uchun ushbu

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x \frac{\varphi(t)}{(x-t)^{1-\alpha}} dt, \quad x > a,$$

Abel tenglamasining

$$\varphi(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dx} \int_a^x \frac{f(t)}{(x-t)^{\alpha}} dt, \quad 0 < \alpha < 1$$

yechimidan foydalaniladi.

Shu yerda ta'kidlash lozimki, kasr tartibli hosilaning Riman-Liuvill va Kaputo (va x.k) ma'nosidagi ta'riflari mavjud.

Ta'rif. $[a, b]$ kesmada berilgan $f(x)$ funksiya uchun ushbu

$$(D_{a+}^{\alpha}f)(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dx} \int_a^x \frac{f(t)}{(x-t)^{\alpha}} dt, \quad (3)$$

va

$$(D_{b-}^{\alpha}f)(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dx} \int_x^b \frac{f(t)}{(t-x)^{\alpha}} dt, \quad 0 < \alpha < 1 \quad (4)$$

formulalar mos ravishda Riman-Liuvill ma'nosidagi chap tomonlama va o'ng tomonlama α kasr tartibli hosila deyiladi. Riman-Liuvill ma'nosidagi hosila uchun $D_{RL}^{\alpha} f(x)$ belgi ham ishlatiladi.

$$\alpha > 0, n = [\alpha] + 1 - \alpha \text{ dan kichik bo'lmagan eng kichik butun son bo'lsin.}$$

Ta'rif. Kaputo ma'nosidagi α kasr tartibli hosila deb

$${}^C D^{\alpha} f(x) = J^{n-\alpha} \left(f^{(n)}(x) \right)$$

formulaga aytiladi, bu yerda $J^{\beta} g(x) = (I_{0+}^{\beta} g(x))$ - Riman-Liuvill ma'nosidagi $\beta > 0$ kasr tartibli integral:

$$J^{\beta} g(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_0^x (x-t)^{\beta-1} g(t) dt.$$

Kaputo ma'nosidagi kasr tartibli hosilani aniqlash uchun asosiy shart $f^{(k)}(0)$, $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1$ oddiy hosilalarni mavjudligi va chekli bo'lishidir. Bular Kaputo ma'nosidagi kasr tartibli hosila ishtirok etadigan muammolarda boshlang'ch shart sifatida ishtirok etadi.

Qulaylik uchun Riman-Liuvill va Kaputo ma'nosidagi kasr tartibli hosilalar quyidagicha belgilanadi ($0 < \alpha < 1$):

$$D_{RL}^{\alpha} f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dx} \int_0^x (x-t)^{-\alpha} f(t) dt,$$

$$D_C^{\alpha} f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \int_0^x (x-t)^{-\alpha} f'(t) dt.$$

Ma'lumki, variatsion hisob nazariyasida funksiyaning butun tartibli hosilalariga bog'liq bo'lgan ko'plab funkcionallar o'rganiladi [10-14], jumladan eng sodda funksional

$$J[y] = \int_a^b F(x, y(x), y'(x)) dx$$

ko'rinishdadir.

Endi yuqoridagi ko'rinishga ega bo'lgan funkcionallarni funksiyaning kasr tartibli hosilalariga bog'liq bo'lgan funkcionallarini ko'rib o'tamiz.

Ta'rif. Ushbu ko'rinishdagi

$$J[y] = \int_a^b F(x, y(x), {}^C D_{a+}^{\alpha} y(x)) dx, \quad 0 < \alpha < 1$$

funksional funksiyaning Kaputo tipidagi kasr tartibli hosilalasi qatnashgan funksional deyiladi, bu yerda, $y(x)$ - qidirilayotgan funksiya, ${}^C D_{a+}^{\alpha}$ - Kaputo ma'nosidagi kasr tartibli hosila, F - Lagranj funksiyasi.

Agar $y(a)=y(b)=0$ bo'lsa, u holda funksionalga mos Eyler-Lagranj tenglamasi

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial y} + {}_x D_{b-}^{\alpha} \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial ({}^C D_{a+}^{\alpha} y)} \right) = 0$$

ko'rinishda bo'ladi va u kasr tartibli hosilali Eyler-Lagranj tenglamasi deyiladi.

Misol uchun agar funksional

$$J[y] = \frac{1}{2} \int_a^b \left({}^C D_{a+}^\alpha y(x) \right)^2 dx$$

ko`rinishda bo`lsa, u holda

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial \left({}^C D_{a+}^\alpha y \right)} = {}^C D_{a+}^\alpha y$$

bo`lib, funksionalga mos Eyler-Lagranj tenglamasi

$${}_x D_{b-}^\alpha \left({}^C D_{a+}^\alpha y \right) = 0$$

bo`ladi. Bu kasr tartibli hosilali differensial tenglamadan iborat. Tenglamani chap tomonini kasr tartibli Laplas operatori ham deyiladi. Shuning uchun, tenglamani kasr tartibli Laplas tenglamasi deyish mumkin.

Ta`rif. Ushbu ko`rinishdagi

$$J[y] = \int_a^b F(x, y, D_{a+}^\alpha y) dx$$

funksional funksiyaning Riman-Liuvill tipidagi kasr tartibli hosilalasi qatnashgan funksional deyiladi, bu yerda, $y(x)$ - qidirilayotgan funksiya, D_{a+}^α - Riman-Liuvill ma`nosidagi kasr tartibli hosila, F - Lagranj funksiyasi.

Ushbu funksionalga mos Eyler-Lagranj tenglamasi

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial y} + {}_x D_{b-}^\alpha \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial \left(D_{a+}^\alpha y \right)} \right) = 0$$

ko`rinishda bo`ladi. Bu yerda, **boshlang`ich shartlar** talqini murakkabroq va alohida masala hisoblanadi. Shuning uchun bu haqida to`htalmaymiz.

Ta`rif. Ushbu ko`rinishdagi

$$J[y] = \int_a^b F(x, y, {}^C D_{a+}^\alpha y, {}^C D_{a+}^\beta y) dx, \quad 0 < \alpha < \beta < 1$$

funksional funksiyaning yuqori tartibli Kaputo tipidagi kasr tartibli hosilalasi qatnashgan funksional deyiladi, bu yerda, $y(x)$ - qidirilayotgan funksiya, ${}^C D_{a+}^\alpha$ va ${}^C D_{a+}^\beta$ - Kaputo ma`nosidagi kasr tartibli hosilalar, F - Lagranj funksiyasi.

Ushbu funksionalga mos Eyler-Lagranj tenglamasi

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial y} + {}_x D_{b-}^\alpha \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial \left({}^C D_{a+}^\alpha y \right)} \right) + {}_x D_{b-}^\beta \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial \left({}^C D_{a+}^\beta y \right)} \right) = 0$$

ko`rinishda bo`ladi.

Klassik hosila, ya`ni butun tartibli va kasr tartibli hosilalar qatnashgan funkcionallar tushunchasini ham kiritish mumkin.

Ta`rif. Ushbu ko`rinishdagi

$$J[y] = \int_a^b F(x, y(x), y'(x), \dots, y^{(n)}(x), {}^C D_{a+}^\alpha y(x)) dx, \quad 0 < \alpha < 1$$

funksional funksiyaning oddiy hosilalari va Kaputo tipidagi kasr tartibli hosilalari qatnashgan (gibrid) funksional deyiladi, bu yerda, $y(x)$ - qidirilayotgan funksiya, ${}^C D_{a+}^\alpha$ - Kaputo ma'nosidagi kasr tartibli hosila, F - Lagranj funksiyasi.

Misol. $n = 2$ uchun.

$$J[y] = \int_a^b \left[\left({}^C D_a^\alpha y \right)^2 + \mu (y'')^2 \right] dx, \quad 0 < \alpha < 1.$$

Bu funksionalga mos Eyler-Lagranj tenglamasi

$${}_x D_b^\alpha \left({}^C D_a^\alpha y \right) + \mu \frac{d^4 y}{dx^4} = 0$$

bo'ladi. Bu to'rtinchi tartibli kasr atrtibli hosila qatnashgan differensial tenglama bo'lib, **xotirali elastik (qovushqoq elastik) tizimlarga doir ayrim amaliy masalalarni matematik modelini ifodalaydi.**

Yuqorida bayon qilinganlardan kelib chiqib quyidagicha xulosa qilish mumkin: Kasr tartibli Eyler-Lagranj tenglamasi hosil bo'lishi uchun funksional ifodasida funksiyaning Kaputo yoki Riman-Liuvill ma'nosidagi kasr tartibli hosilasi ishtirok etishi zarur. Variatsiyalash jarayonida kasr tartibli integrallash bo'yicha qismlarga ajratish formulasidan foydalaniladi, natijada klassik Eyler-Lagranj tenglamasining kasr tartibli analogi olinadi. Va aksincha, qaralayotgan funksional ifodasida funksiyaning Caputo yoki Riman-Liuvill ma'nosidagi kasr tartibli hosilasi ishtirok etsa, uning Eyler-Lagranj tenglamasi kasr tartibli differensial tenglamadan iborat bo'ladi.

Yuqorida Kaputo tipidagi kasr tartibli hosilalari qatnashgan

$$J[y] = \int_a^b F(x, y(x), {}^C D_{a+}^\alpha y(x)) dx, \quad 0 < \alpha < 1$$

funksionalga mos Eyler-Lagranj tenglamasi

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial y} + {}_x D_{b-}^\alpha \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial ({}^C D_{a+}^\alpha y)} \right) = 0$$

bo'lishi aytilgan edi. Endi shuni teorema sifatida shakllantiramiz.

Teorema. Bizga Kaputo tipidagi kasr tartibli hosilalari qatnashgan

$$J[y] = \int_a^b F(x, y(x), {}^C D_{a+}^\alpha y(x)) dx, \quad 0 < \alpha < 1$$
 funksional berilgan bo'lsin, bu

yerda $F \in C^1$, $y \in AC[a, b]$, ya'ni $y(x) [a, b]$ da absolyut uzluksiz. Agar $y(x)$ funksiya quyidagi $y(a) = y_0$ boshlang'ich shartni qanoatlantiruvchi **ekstremal** bo'lsa, u holda $y(x)$ quyidagi **umumlashgan kasr tartibli Eyler-Lagranj tenglamasini** qanoatlantiradi:

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial y}(x, y, v) + D_{b-}^\alpha \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial v}(x, y, v) \right) = 0, \quad v = {}^C D_{a+}^\alpha y(x),$$

hamda qo'shimcha tabiiy boshlang'ich shart bajariladi:

$$I_{b^-}^{1-\alpha} \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial v} \right) \Big|_{x=a} = 0.$$

Yuqorida ko'rgan funksionallarimiz bir o'zgaruvchili funksiya va uning hosilalari qatnashgan funksionallar edi. Ammo ko'plab amaliy masalalar xususiy hosilali differensial tenglamalar bilan to'la va aniq ifodalanadi va bunday tenglamalarga mos funksionallar bir necha argumentli funksiyalar hamda ularning xususiy hosilalariga bog'liq bo'ladi.

Masalan ushbu integro-differensial tenglamani ko'raylik[18]:

$$m \frac{\partial^2 W(x,t)}{\partial t^2} + EJ \left(\frac{\partial^4 W(x,t)}{\partial x^4} - \int_0^t \frac{Ae^{-\beta(t-\tau)}}{(t-\tau)^{1-\alpha}} \frac{\partial^4 W(x,\tau)}{\partial x^4} d\tau \right) - P \frac{\partial^2 W(x,t)}{\partial x^2} = q(x,t)$$

Bu tenglama bo'ylama siquvchi P kuch va ko'ndalang $q(x,t)$ kuch ta'sirida l uzunlikdagi qovushqoq elastik sterjenning tebranish tenglamasidir.

Bu yerda, m - birlik uzunlikga mos massa, E - elastiklik moduli, J - inrsiya momenti, $W(x,t)$ - egilish, $R(t) = \frac{Ae^{-\beta t}}{t^\alpha}$ - Koltunov-Rijanitsinning relaksatsiya yadrosi[18], A - qovushqoqlik koeffitsenti, $\beta > 0, 0 < \alpha < 1$.

Tenglamadagi $\int_0^t \frac{Ae^{-\beta(t-\tau)}}{(t-\tau)^{1-\alpha}} \frac{\partial^4 W(x,\tau)}{\partial x^4} d\tau$ hadni qarajak, bu

yerdagi $\frac{1}{(t-\tau)^{1-\alpha}}$ ifoda odatda α - kasr tartibli operatorlarning

yadrosi

hisoblanadi. $e^{-\beta(t-\tau)}$ ko'paytuvchisi esa bu operatorning eksponensial tartibga solingan yoki umumlashtirilgan ko'rinishi ekanligini anglatadi.

Agar Riman-Liuivill ma'nosidagi kasr tartibli hosilani $D_t^{\alpha,\beta}$ kabi belgilasak (yoki umumiy holatda kasr tartibli integral operatorni I^α desak), tenglamani ixchamroq ko'rinishda yozish mumkin, ya'ni tenglama quyidagi ko'rinishga keladi:

$$m \frac{\partial^2 W(x,t)}{\partial t^2} + EJ \left(\frac{\partial^4 W(x,t)}{\partial x^4} - A \cdot D_t^{\alpha,\beta} \left[\frac{\partial^4 W(x,t)}{\partial x^4} \right] \right) - P \frac{\partial^2 W(x,t)}{\partial x^2} = q(x,t)$$

Bu tenglamani Kaputo ma'nosidagi kasr tartibli hosila orqali quyidagicha yozish mumkin:

$$m \frac{\partial^2 W(x,t)}{\partial t^2} + EJ \left(\frac{\partial^4 W(x,t)}{\partial x^4} - A \cdot \Gamma(\alpha) \cdot {}^c D_{0,t}^{\alpha,\beta} \left[\frac{\partial^4 W(x,t)}{\partial x^4} \right] \right) - P \frac{\partial^2 W(x,t)}{\partial x^2} = q(x,t)$$

Keltirilgan integro-differensial tenglama uchun variatsion hisob tamoyillariga ko'ra funksionalni (ya'ni, energiyani ifodalovchi ifodani) topish uchun biz Gamilton prinsipidan yoki Lagranj funksiyasidan foydalanamiz.

Funksional $J(W)$ quyidagi umumiy ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi:

$$J(W) = \int_0^t \int_0^l L dx dt$$

Bu yerda L Lagranj funksiyasi bo'lib, u kinetik energiya, potensial energiya va tashqi kuchlar ishining ayirmasidan iborat. Lagranj funksiyasi qaralayotgan masala uchun quyidagi qismlardan iborat bo'ladi:

$$T = \frac{1}{2} m \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial t} \right)^2 - \text{kinetik energiya}; \quad U = \frac{1}{2} EJ \left(\frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 - \text{egilish energiyasi};$$

$$A_P = \frac{1}{2} P \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial x} \right)^2 - P \text{ kuchning ishi}; \quad \Phi = \frac{1}{2} EJ \cdot A \int_0^t \frac{e^{-\beta(t-\tau)}}{(t-\tau)^{1-\alpha}} \frac{\partial^2 W(x,t)}{\partial x^2} \frac{\partial^2 W(x,\tau)}{\partial x^2} d\tau -$$

qovushqoq elastik qism (bu qism dissipativ (energiya yutilishi) xarakterga ega bo'lgani uchun odatda variatsion hisobda qovushqoq elastik potensial ko'rinishida qo'shiladi); $A_q = \frac{1}{2} q(x,t)W$

- q tashqi yuklamaning potentsiali.

Demak, yuqoridagi integro-differensial tenglamaga mos keluvchi funksional quyidagi ko'rinishda yoziladi:

$$J(W) = \int_0^t \int_0^l \left[\frac{1}{2} m \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial t} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} EJ \left(\frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 + \frac{EJ \cdot A}{2} \left(\int_0^t \frac{e^{-\beta(t-\tau)}}{(t-\tau)^{1-\alpha}} \frac{\partial^2 W(x,\tau)}{\partial x^2} d\tau \right) \frac{\partial^2 W(x,t)}{\partial x^2} + \right. \\ \left. + \frac{1}{2} P \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2} q(x,t)W \right] dx dt.$$

Umumlashgan kasr tartibli integral operatorni quyidagicha kiritsak

$(I_{0,t}^{\alpha,\beta} \phi)(t) = \int_0^t \frac{e^{-\beta(t-\tau)}}{(t-\tau)^{1-\alpha}} \phi(\tau) d\tau$ u holda funksional quyidagicha yoziladi:

$$J(W) = \int_0^t \int_0^l \left[\frac{1}{2} m \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial t} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} EJ \left(\frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 + \frac{EJ \cdot A}{2} \left(I_{0,t}^{\alpha,\beta} \left[\frac{\partial^2 W(x,t)}{\partial x^2} \right] \right) \frac{\partial^2 W(x,t)}{\partial x^2} + \right. \\ \left. + \frac{1}{2} P \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2} q(x,t)W \right] dx dt.$$

Bu funksionaldan W bo'yicha variatsiya olib nolga tenglasak, yuqoridagi kasr tartibli hosila qatnashgan xususiy hosilali differensial tenglama kelib chiqadi.

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